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PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF ORGANIZING AND CARRYING OUT COMPREHENSIVE SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL ASSESSMENT OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH

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Annotation: Evaluation of the effectiveness of scientific and technical projects includes expert research carried out by different specialties, when a variety of interdisciplinary knowledge and methodological support are needed to achieve the goal. The fundamental problems of methodological support for complex scientific and technical expertise are formulated. The main forms and features of carrying out complex scientific and technical expertise are singled out. Scientific and methodological approaches to the expert study of informative sources on the effectiveness of scientific research and development are proposed. The unifying elements of conducting a comprehensive expertise are formulated, criteria for the commission examinations conclusions objective assessments scientific validity are established.

Keywords: scientific expertise, methodological support, high technologies, innovations, venture organizations

ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ И ПРОВЕДЕНИЯ КОМПЛЕКСНОЙ НАУЧНО-ТЕХНИЧЕСКОЙ ОЦЕНКИ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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Аннотация: К оценке эффективности научно-технических проектов относятся экспертные исследования, проводимые разными специальностями, когда для достижения цели необходимы разнообразные междисциплинарные знания и методическое обеспечение. Сформулированы основные проблемы методического обеспечения комплексной научно-технической экспертизы. Выделены основные формы и особенности проведения комплексной научно-технической экспертизы. Предложены научно-методические подходы к экспертному изучению информационных источников на предмет эффективности научных исследований и разработок. Сформулированы объединяющие элементы проведения комплексной экспертизы, установлены критерии научной обоснованности заключений комиссий экспертиз.

Ключевые слова: научная экспертиза, методическое обеспечение, высокие технологии, инновации, венчурные организации

It is difficult to overestimate the importance of studying the features of organizing complex examinations and expert studies on the economic issues of innovative research. However, despite the constant interest of scientists in improving the organization and methodology of scientific and technical expertise, a number of applied issues still remain unresolved, and the features of conducting complex expertise and expert

studies on economic issues for some objects are generally ignored by previous studies [1, 2].

The purpose of the article is to study the features of the organization of complex scientific and technical expertise and expert research on the economic issues of innovative research. In modern conditions, a significant number of institutional actors and scientists become participants in innovative research. As a rule, the preferred option for studying the effectiveness of scientific projects is the conduct of an economic examination by a qualified specialist. Expertise is a study based on special knowledge in the field of science and technology of innovative objects, phenomena and processes in order to provide an opinion on issues that are the subject of the effectiveness and efficiency of innovative research [3, 4]. Solving the issues of documentary justification of losses by indicators of financial statements of venture scientific and technical organizations for a certain period (recognition of current receivables as uncollectible) does not apply to the tasks of economic expertise of innovative projects. At the same time, in the process of organizing and conducting a comprehensive scientific and technical assessment of innovative research, it is necessary to consider the following aspects: whether the conclusions of the audit report regarding the misuse of budget funds received by a venture scientific and technical organization under the budget target program are documented; whether there are indicators of the financial and economic condition of the venture scientific and technical organization for the period, signs of bringing to bankruptcy, fictitious bankruptcy, hidden bankruptcy; whether the conclusions of the audit report on the presence of debts for the payment of remuneration to scientific employees by the venture scientific and technical organization are documented; whether the calculation of dividends to be paid by the venture scientific and technical organization to the owner of corporate rights for a certain period is documented and statutory; whether the conclusions indicated in the inspection report of the controlling body on the overstatement of the volume of public procurement by a certain amount are documented in comparison with the terms of the contract concluded as a result of competitive bidding; whether the conclusions of the inspection report of the controlling body regarding the unreasonable transfer of budgetary funds are documented, taking into account the conclusions of other types of examinations; whether the calculation of the borrower's debt

(on payment of interest on the loan and repayment of the principal amount of the debt) to the bank complies with the conditions of the loan agreement concluded between the said parties and settlement documents for the issuance and repayment of the loan under this loan agreement; whether the method of accruing interest by the bank under the loan agreement meets the requirements of the regulation on bank lending.

To determine which documents should be provided to an expert for research in each specific case, it is advisable to get advice from an expert economist. To conduct a study, it is necessary to provide scientific and technical materials that are considered by the relevant development institution that appointed the examination or by the head of the expert scientific and technical institution.

During the expertise (expert studies) in order to fulfill a certain expert task, the experts apply appropriate research methods, methods for conducting complex scientific and technical expertise. Items and documents that are the objects of expert examination shall be returned to the actor who appointed the examination, together with the conclusion of the examination or a notice of the impossibility of providing an opinion. Large scientific and technological installations and other objects that are not subject to shipment are examined in a venture scientific and technical organization personally or by a representative on behalf of the organization that appointed the examination.

In general, the procedure for appointing and conducting complex scientific and technical examinations and expert studies on economic issues, as well as the rights, duties and responsibilities of experts in procedural terms, are similar [5, 6]. The basis for conducting a comprehensive examination is the relevant decision of the executive authority, or an agreement with an expert or an expert scientific and technical institution – if the examination is carried out on the order of other persons.

In the process of organizing and conducting a comprehensive scientific and technical assessment of innovative research, it is important to document the results of examinations and expert studies, the features of choosing research methods and methods for conducting feasibility studies, as well as improving regulatory documents for organizing complex examinations and expert studies on economic questions.

Conducting complex expert studies represent complex forms of integration of special knowledge with the involvement of relevant specialists. When analyzing complex scientific and technical productions in innovative practice, an integrated approach to expert research of informative sources is determined to be effective [7, 8]. Expert studies of a complex nature are becoming increasingly important, ensuring the reliability of conclusions in complex scientific and technical productions and economic disputes [9, 10]. The need to regulate comprehensive examinations is very important, since such an examination has its own subjects of study, requiring the use of various fields of knowledge, specifics both in terms of purpose and in terms of the powers and responsibilities of experts. Such an examination is usually carried out by at least two specialists belonging to different branches of knowledge [11, 12]. When conducting complex examinations, various generic accumulated knowledge is used, new methods of natural and technical sciences are used, which can help in establishing the truth in the process of evaluating the effectiveness of high-tech results [13, 14].

The rapid growth in the use of various sciences in the field of scientific and technical expertise is primarily associated with the improvement of the mechanism for implementing complex scientific and technical programs, the use of modern methods of interdisciplinary research, which encourages the use of knowledge in various fields of science and technology, makes it important to improve the conduct of research to determine the relevance and feasibility of scientific results.

The organization and conduct of a comprehensive scientific and technical assessment of innovative research is carried out by using special studies based on various knowledge to provide answers to the questions raised, using the methods of modern expert knowledge, as one of the more effective means of determining effectiveness.

Separate scientific studies confirm that the modern needs of practice for the widespread introduction of the complexity of expertise of a high scientific level are a practical necessity in the innovation sphere [15, 16].

A comprehensive examination is an expert study carried out by experts of different specialties, when a variety of knowledge of other sciences is needed to achieve the goal. In the commission expertise, each specialist is responsible for the validity of the conclusions. If an expert has

knowledge from various branches of science, he can conduct research independently.

The main forms of implementation of a comprehensive examination in practice are: an expert study, which is carried out by several experts and signed by them a conclusion on the innovative research goal achievement; a separate study of each expert of the general subject of study with the determination of intermediate conclusions on the effectiveness of scientific research.

In the first case, the expert, on the basis of other special knowledge, participates in the formation of a general conclusion. In the second case, the expert must have complex specialized knowledge in order to draw his conclusions into the general act of the study. Other experts may draw up separate acts or relevant sections of the main act based on the results of their research. In this case, the experts signing the joint act refer to the results of intermediate studies as one of the grounds for their conclusion.

The main features of complex scientific and technical expertise are proposed to include the following: one object is investigated by all involved experts; different research methods are used; the presence of different competencies of interacting experts and the distribution of functions; the similarity of systems of information units that provide a common understanding, control and evaluation; the presence of a single formulation based on the integration of the obtained heterogeneous data through their joint assessment by all experts.

There is a fundamental problem of methodological support for complex scientific and technical expertise, the solution to the problem is the creation of a methodology for appointing and conducting interdisciplinary complex scientific and technical expertise. The legal support for establishing criteria for selecting the leading expert institution of different departments has not been resolved; the rules for conducting an examination by different experts in the commission are not defined; terms for conducting complex interdepartmental examinations have not been determined; the criteria for appointing the head of the interdepartmental complex expertise are not defined; the grounds for filing a petition by the leading expert institution are unclear, etc. Also, in the legal aspect, the issue of establishing criteria for the scientific validity of objective assessments of the conclusions of commission examinations has not been settled.

The requirements of modern practice of innovation activity necessitate a comprehensive examination of the implementation and use in the study of the developed modern scientific and technological achievements, based on the development of related sciences. The main problem is the development of a methodology for creating and conducting new complex sectoral and interdepartmental scientific and technical expertise at a high scientific level.

The basic principles of organizing comprehensive scientific and technical expertise should not depend on the field of scientific research. The main unifying element for conducting a comprehensive scientific and technical expertise is the presence of a common subject of study for various fields of knowledge, the study of which is carried out based on general methods and rules governing such a study, and the results of each expert should be criterial reflected in the general conclusion.

Venture scientific and technical organizations actively use information systems and information technologies in the process of implementing scientific research and development [17, 18]. Modern information systems built based on leading information technologies can significantly speed up the search and processing of the necessary information, increase its significance, reliability, which increases the competitive advantages of the enterprise [19, 20].

To develop and implement an information system, it is necessary to make a number of capital investments in the development of projects for the implementation of preparatory work, the purchase of equipment, software, and training. The cost of an information system is directly proportional to the innovation activity areas range covered by automation.

Therefore, the main task in making a decision on the implementation of an information system for a comprehensive scientific and technical assessment of innovative research in an enterprise is to assess the economic benefits that the enterprise will receive from the operation of the information system compared to the costs necessary for its development and implementation.

Economic efficiency is defined as the ratio of results to costs and is often used as a qualitative characteristic of the effectiveness of research and development.

The economic effect is defined as the difference between the income from the activity and the costs of its implementation, expressed in

monetary terms. This indicator is used to solve the problems of choosing the optimal course of action and, in essence, specifies the concept of efficiency.

Therefore, the definition of economic efficiency is actually a comparison of the results obtained from investments with the costs (in monetary terms) for its implementation and operation.

The criteria for scientific validity of objective assessments of the conclusions of commission examinations should include the following groups: economic, scientific and technical, social and environmental. The economic effect can be both potential and actual, while the scientific, technical, social and environmental effect can only be manifested potentially. When evaluating the effectiveness of using the information system for a comprehensive scientific and technical assessment of innovative research, it must be taken into account that its development and implementation contains a number of stages: the formation of requirements for an information system; concept development; technical task; preliminary design; technical project; working documentation; commissioning; maintenance of the information system.

The list of stages may vary depending on the characteristics of venture scientific and technical organizations and the agreement between the system developer and its customer.

The development and implementation of an information system can be considered an innovative project, since innovation is a creative process through the creation of new consumer values, the use of which requires users to change the usual stereotypes of their activities and their skills. This definition covers a new product or service, a method of production, innovations in financial, research and other fields, any improvement that provides cost savings or creates conditions for such savings.

According to the classification features of innovations, the development and implementation of information technologies for a comprehensive scientific and technical assessment of innovative research is an organizational innovation that leads to the redistribution of managerial functions, reduces the cost of organizing the innovation process, and improves the process of making managerial decisions. Evaluation of the effectiveness of such information systems is carried out as a calculation of the effectiveness of an innovative project.

After calculating the net present value (NPV), it is necessary to analyze the risk of an innovative project. After comparing the magnitude of the risk and the magnitude of the NPV, one can judge the feasibility of implementing an information system project.

The instability of modern economic conditions for the functioning of venture scientific and technical organizations, the impossibility of developing clear forecasts of monetary and technical and economic characteristics of activities, the lack of information to take into account inflationary actions hinder the full use of monetary and probabilistic methods.

It is proposed to use a qualitative approach to assess the economic efficiency of introducing information systems for a comprehensive scientific and technical assessment of innovative research. It is necessary to carry out a systematic analysis of the conditions for the functioning of an automated information system, use indicators that characterize the technical and software support of specialists of venture scientific and technical organizations and reflect the costs of technical, software and organizational support of the information system.

The market of modern software tools offers a wide range of software systems that have a component structure and allow to automate accounting, analytical, planning activities and the development of management decisions. Therefore, the issue of determining the effectiveness of introducing a new software product into the information management system of a venture scientific and technical organization is relevant.

At the present stage of economic development, most venture scientific and technical organizations have information management systems with a built-in computer form of accounting. Management decisions lead to the need to replace outdated software and expand the functions of existing management systems, so an important issue is to determine the effectiveness of replacing existing software with a more progressive one for a comprehensive scientific and technical assessment of innovative research. Therefore, there is a need to systematize the methodology for calculating the effectiveness of the introduction of new software for the information system for managing innovative research. It is proposed to carry out such a calculation in two stages. First, the calculation of absolute indicators of economic efficiency is the determination of the

reduction in annual labor costs for innovation, and then the calculation of the economic efficiency of introducing new management information system software based on the method of payment flows using a difference approach.

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